

A ROBUST DESIGN METHODOLOGY PROCESS

Why?

There is a need to identify Robust Design Methodology (RDM) practices suitable for all parts of product development (PD). The company studied wanted to develop a RDM sub-process in their PD process.

What?

The purpose of this paper is to describe and evaluate a process for RDM practices throughout PD.

How?

An empirical study by two researchers together with a practitioner, based on an action research approach.

Where?

A study at a Swedish medium-sized (250 employees) manufacturing company, aiming to develop a Product Robustness Process (PRP) as a sub-process in their product development. The company is developing, producing and selling their own patented high-tech product.

Key Characteristics

Three crucial characteristics of the PRP:

- 1) Focus on practices rather than tools.
- 2) The PRP is fully integrated with the PD process, and follow-up of RDM practices are included at the gate reviews.
- 3) The PRP is followed up on RDM related outcomes.

The Product Robustness Process

One approach: P-diagram

